

Combined TOPSIS Technique for MAGDM Based on the Distance Measures and CRITIC under Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets and Applications to Quality Evaluation of Whole Process Engineering Consulting Service Modes

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Abstract: According to survey data released by the National Bureau of Statistics, from 2011 to 2022, the total output value of China's construction industry showed an increasing trend year by year. From 2018 to 2021, infrastructure investment has always maintained a positive growth, indicating that the current construction industry is in a rapid development stage. In order to improve the development quality of the construction industry as much as possible, it is of great significance to develop the whole Process engineering consulting service model. The quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is MAGDM. The single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNSs) is useful tool to cope with uncertain information during the quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes. In this paper, the single-valued neutrosophic number combined TOPSIS (SVNN-CTOPSIS) model based on single-valued neutrosophic number Hamming distances (SVNNHD) and single-valued neutrosophic number Euclidean distance (SVNNED) is formed to cope with the MAGDM. The CRITIC model is utilized to obtain the weight numbers in light with the SVNNHD and SVNNED under SVNSs. Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is utilized to verify SVNN-CTOPSIS model. The main contributions of this study are formed: (1) the CRITIC model is formed to obtain the weight numbers in light with SVNNHD and SVNNED;

(2) the SVN-CTOPSIS model is formed in light with SVNHD and SVNED under SVNs;
(3) Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is employed to verify SVN-CTOPSIS model.

Keywords: MAGDM; SVNs; TOPSIS; CRITIC model; performance evaluation

1. Introduction

Against the backdrop of rapid development in the construction industry, the investment entities of engineering projects are developing in a diversified direction[1, 2]. Traditional "fragmented" consulting services are no longer able to effectively meet the investment needs of investors. In the face of such situations, the Opinions on Promoting the Sustainable and Healthy Development of the Construction Industry (Guo Ban Fa [2017] No. 19) put forward for the first time the idea of cultivating the whole process engineering consulting, which has promoted the transformation of China's engineering consulting work from the past professional division of labor model to the whole process, cross stage integration model[3-5]. In the practical application of the consortium consulting service model[6, 7], a project will be handed over to two or more consulting units to jointly carry out the whole process engineering consulting services of engineering projects, and the lead party will be responsible for the coordination of the consulting business during the service development process. In the current process engineering consulting service development process, there are relatively many factors to apply the consortium consulting service model. Common factors include large project scale, complex work content, and lack of professional service qualifications of some consulting units. Considering that the consortium consulting service model needs to unite multiple consulting units in the application process, in order to improve the reliability of consulting services and the quality of the division of responsibilities, the management relationship and responsibilities of each consulting unit need to be noted in the contract before the application of the consortium consulting service model, so as to lay a good foundation for the orderly development of the whole process engineering consulting services. The integrated whole process consulting service model is a work mode in which a consulting unit is responsible for coordinating the entire process consulting work of engineering projects[8-10]. Due to the comprehensive range of consulting services covered by the service model, only a few consulting units in the current consulting service industry have the qualifications and experience to apply the consulting service model. Therefore, compared to other consulting service techniques, The application experience of the integrated whole process consulting service model is relatively limited. However, due to the fact that the consulting service model is mainly managed by one unit, the difficulty of consulting service management is relatively low, which can effectively improve the integration level of consulting services[11-13]. The "1+N" part of the combined consulting service mode in the whole Process engineering consulting service work is mainly composed of one consulting unit, which distributes a number of consulting businesses to different consulting units in the form of contracting or combination to complete the consulting services. In this process, the consulting unit is responsible for coordinating the whole Process engineering consulting business. In the current work process of consulting companies, the

"1+N" combined consulting service model is mainly applied to project research and decision-making, bidding agency, survey and design, engineering supervision, cost decision-making, and other work[14-16]. The business combination techniques mainly include the combination of design units and cost analysis units, design units and supervision units, supervision units and bidding agency units Combining design units with survey and supervision units, etc. For the current construction activities of engineering projects, the "1+N" part combination consulting service model is highly similar to the traditional single consulting contract business[14-18]. Therefore, this work model has been widely used in the early stage of the whole process engineering consulting service. In a word, in the process of gradually advancing the supply side structural reform, the construction industry is carrying out the organizational model reform represented by the whole Process engineering consulting. In order to make the whole Process engineering consulting service model better meet the needs of the current development of the construction industry, based on clarifying the shortcomings of the traditional professional engineering consulting service model, the actual situation of the project is analyzed, the development of a more complete and reliable process engineering consulting service model can provide strong support for the smooth implementation of project management[19-21].

With rapid development of GDM issues, MAGDM techniques have greatly attracted academic attention [22-30]. In order to put forward the objective things through employing precise numbers. Zadeh [31] creatively put forward the fuzzy sets (FSs) theory. Atanassov [32] creatively put forward intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs). However, IFSs didn't put forward uncertain membership. In order to manage a more efficient technique, Smarandache [33] creatively put forward the neutrosophic sets(NSs). Zenat, Mahmoud and Amal [34] put forward the TOPSIS model for green supply chain practices under SVNNSs. Ahmed, Nehal and Ibrahim [35] put forward the CRITIC model for coping with the product design in virtual reality under SVNNSs. Abdullallah et al. [36] put forward the AHP-VIKOR model for coping with the Supply chain (SC) networks with neutrosophic theory. Karam et al. [37] put forward the TOPSIS for assessment quality of suppliers under SVNNSs. M. Sabry [38] put forward the CRITIC-EDAS model for urban energy internet assessment by type 2 neutrosophic numbers (T2NNs). Abdullallah et al. [39] put forward the MEREC-CoCoSo for coping with the autonomous vehicles and distributed resources using type-2 neutrosophic numbers (T2NN). The quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is the real-life MAGDM [40-44]. The SVNNSs [45] is useful technique to cope with uncertain information during the quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes. Furthermore, many techniques employed the TOPSIS model [46-49] and CRITIC model [50-54] separately to solve the MAGDM. Unfortunately, few valuable existing works were managed the combined TOPSIS based on SVNNHD and SVNNED under SVNNSs. The main objective of this study is to cope with MAGDM through employing the SVNN-CTOPSIS model with SVNNHD and SVNNED model. Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is utilized to verify SVNN-CTOPSIS model. The main research goals and motivation of this study are formed: (1) the CRITIC model is formed to obtain

the weight numbers in light with SVNND and SVNNED; (2) the SVNN-CTOPSIS model is formed in light with SVNND and SVNNED under SVNNs; (3) Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is employed to verify SVNN-CTOPSIS model.

The remaining sections is formed. The SVNSs is formed in Sect 2. The SVNN-CTOPSIS model is formed for MAGDM in Sect. 3. The quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes and some comparative analyses is formed to verify the SVNN-CTOPSIS model in Sect. 4. The conclusion is formed in Sect. 5.

2. Preliminaries

Wang et al. [45] formed the SVNSs.

Definition 1 [45]. The SVNSs is formed:

$$DA = \{(\mathcal{G}, DT_A(\mathcal{G}), DI_A(\mathcal{G}), DF_A(\mathcal{G})) | \mathcal{G} \in \Theta\} \tag{1}$$

where $DT_A(\mathcal{G}), DI_A(\mathcal{G}), DF_A(\mathcal{G})$ depicts truth membership, indeterminacy membership and falsity membership, $DT_A(\mathcal{G}), DI_A(\mathcal{G}), DF_A(\mathcal{G}) \in [0, 1]$,

$$0 \leq DT_A(\mathcal{G}) + DI_A(\mathcal{G}) + DF_A(\mathcal{G}) \leq 3.$$

Definition 2 [55]. The score value information (SVI) of $DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$ is formed:

$$SVI(DA) = \frac{(2 + DT_A - DI_A - DF_A)}{3}, SVI(DA) \in [0, 1]. \tag{2}$$

$$SVI(DB) = \frac{(2 + DT_B - DI_B - DF_B)}{3}, SVI(DB) \in [0, 1]. \tag{3}$$

Definition 3 [55]. The accuracy value information (AVI) of $DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$ is formed:

$$AVI(DA) = \frac{1 + DT_A - DF_A}{2}, AVI(DA) \in [0, 1]. \tag{4}$$

$$AVI(DB) = \frac{1 + DT_B - DF_B}{2}, AVI(DB) \in [0, 1]. \tag{5}$$

Peng et al. [55] formed the order between two SVNNs.

Definition 4[55]. Let $DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$, let

$$SVI(DA) = \frac{(2 + DT_A - DI_A - DF_A)}{3} \quad \text{and} \quad SVI(DB) = \frac{(2 + DT_B - DI_B - DF_B)}{3} , \quad \text{and}$$

let $AVI(DA) = \frac{1 + DT_A - DF_A}{2}$ and $AVI(DB) = \frac{1 + DT_B - DF_B}{2}$, if

$SVI(DA) < SVI(DB)$, then: $DA < DB$; if $SVI(DA) = SVI(DB)$, then:

(1)if $AVI(DA) = AVI(DB)$, then $DA = DB$; (2) if $AVI(DA) > AVI(DB)$, then:

$DA < DB$.

Definition 5[45]. Let $DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$ be

SVNNs, the following operations are formed:

- (1) $DA \oplus DB = (DT_A + DT_B - DT_A DT_B, DI_A DI_B, DF_A DF_B)$;
- (2) $DA \otimes DB = (DT_A DT_B, DI_A + DI_B - DI_A DI_B, DF_A + DF_B - DF_A DF_B)$;
- (3) $\pi DA = (1 - (1 - DT_A)^\pi, (DI_A)^\pi, (DF_A)^\pi), \pi > 0$;
- (4) $(DA)^\pi = ((DT_A)^\pi, (DI_A)^\pi, 1 - (1 - DF_A)^\pi), \pi > 0$.

Definition 6 [56]. Let $DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$, then SVNN

Hamming distance (SVNNHD) and SVNN Euclidean distance (SVNNED) between

$DA = (DT_A, DI_A, DF_A)$ and $DB = (DT_B, DI_B, DF_B)$ is formed:

$$SVNNHD(DA, DB) = \frac{1}{3} (|DT_A - DT_B| + |DI_A - DI_B| + |DF_A - DF_B|) \quad (6)$$

$$SVNNED(DA, DB) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_A - DT_B|^2 + |DI_A - DI_B|^2 + |DF_A - DF_B|^2)} \quad (7)$$

The SVNNWA & SVNNWG model are formed.

Definition 8 [55]. If $DA_j = (DT_j, DI_j, DF_j)$, the SVNNWA operator is formed:

$$SVNNWA_{dw} (DA_1, DA_2, \dots, DA_n) = \bigoplus_{j=1}^n (dw_j DA_j) \quad (8)$$

$$= \left(1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - DT_j)^{dw_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (DI_j)^{dw_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (DF_j)^{dw_j} \right)$$

with weight $dw=(dw_1, dw_2, \dots, dw_n)^T$, $\sum_{j=1}^n dw_j = 1$.

Definition 9 [55]. If $DA_j = (DT_j, DI_j, DF_j)$, the SVNNG model is formed::

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SVNNG}_{dw}(DA_1, DA_2, \dots, DA_n) &= \bigotimes_{j=1}^n (DA_j)^{dw_j} \\ &= \left(\prod_{j=1}^n (DT_j)^{dw_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - DI_j)^{dw_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - DF_j)^{dw_j} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

with weight $dw=(dw_1, dw_2, \dots, dw_n)^T$, $\sum_{j=1}^n dw_j = 1$.

3.

4. SVNNG-CTOPSIS FOR MAGDM IN LIGHT WITH SVNNGHD AND SVNNGED

Then, the SVNNG-CTOPSIS model is formed for MAGDM. Let $DY=(DY_1, DY_2, \dots, DY_m)$ be alternatives. Let $DZ=(DZ_1, DZ_2, \dots, DZ_n)$ be attributes, $dw=\{dw_1, dw_2, \dots, dw_n\}$ be weight for $DZ=(DZ_1, DZ_2, \dots, DZ_n)$, where $dw_j \in [0,1], \sum_{j=1}^n dw_j = 1$. Assume DMs $DX=\{DX_1, DX_2, \dots, DX_l\}$ with weight $d\omega=\{d\omega_1, d\omega_2, \dots, d\omega_l\}$, $d\omega_k \in [0,1], \sum_{k=1}^l d\omega_k = 1$. And $DR^{(k)} = (DR_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n} = (DT_{ij}^{(k)}, DI_{ij}^{(k)}, DF_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n}$ is called as group SVNNG-matrix. The calculating procedures are formed (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. SVN-CTOPSIS for MAGDM in light with SVNHD and SVNED based on CRITIC technique

Step 1. Form group SVN-matrix $DR^{(k)} = \left(DR_{ij}^{(k)} \right)_{m \times n} = \left(DT_{ij}^{(k)}, DI_{ij}^{(k)}, DF_{ij}^{(k)} \right)_{m \times n}$ and single SVN-matrix $DR = \left(DR_{ij} \right)_{m \times n}$ through SVNWG technique.

$$DR^{(k)} = \left[DR_{ij}^{(k)} \right]_{m \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} DR_{11}^{(k)} & DR_{12}^{(k)} & \dots & DR_{1n}^{(k)} \\ DR_{21}^{(k)} & DR_{22}^{(k)} & \dots & DR_{2n}^{(k)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ DR_{m1}^{(k)} & DR_{m2}^{(k)} & \dots & DR_{mn}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$DR = [DR_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} DR_{11} & DR_{12} & \dots & DR_{1n} \\ DR_{21} & DR_{22} & \dots & DR_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ DR_{m1} & DR_{m2} & \dots & DR_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \tag{11}$$

$$\begin{aligned} DR_{ij} &= (DT_{ij}, DI_{ij}, DF_{ij}) \\ &= \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^l (1 - DT_{ij}^{(k)})^{d\omega_k}, \prod_{k=1}^l (DI_{ij}^{(k)})^{d\omega_k}, \prod_{k=1}^l (DF_{ij}^{(k)})^{d\omega_k} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Step 2. Form normalized $DR^N = [DR_{ij}^N]_{m \times n}$ in line with $DR = [DR_{ij}]_{m \times n}$

$$\begin{aligned} DR_{ij}^N &= (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N) \\ &= \begin{cases} (DT_{ij}, DI_{ij}, DF_{ij}), & DZ_j \text{ is the benefit attribute} \\ (DF_{ij}, DI_{ij}, DT_{ij}), & DZ_j \text{ is the cost attribute} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Step 3. Form the weight information through utilizing the CRITIC technique.

The CRITIC [57] is utilized to put forward the weights information.

(1) The SVNN correlation decision coefficient (SVNNCDC) is formed.

$$SVNNCDC_{jt} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (\varphi(DSVNN_{ij}) - \varphi(DSVNN_j)) (\varphi(DSVNN_{it}) - \varphi(DSVNN_t))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (\varphi(DSVNN_{ij}) - \varphi(DSVNN_j))^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (\varphi(DSVNN_{it}) - \varphi(DSVNN_t))^2}}, \tag{14}$$

$j, t = 1, 2, \dots, n,$

where

$$\varphi(DSVNN_j) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (SVI(DR_{ij}^N) + AVI(DR_{ij}^N)),$$

$$\varphi(DSVNN_t) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (SVI(DR_{it}^N) + AVI(DR_{it}^N)),$$

$$\varphi(DSVNN_{ij}) = \frac{1}{2} (SVI(DR_{ij}^N) + AVI(DR_{ij}^N)),$$

$$\varphi(DSVNN_{it}) = \frac{1}{2} (SVI(DR_{it}^N) + AVI(DR_{it}^N)).$$

(2) Form the SVNNSDN standard deviation numbers (SVNNSDN).

$$SVNNSDN_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (\varphi(DSVNN_{ij}) - \varphi(DSVNN_j))^2} \tag{15}$$

(3) Form the attribute weight information.

$$dw_j = \frac{SVNNSDN_j \sum_{t=1}^n (1 - SVNNCDC_{jt})}{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(SVNNSDN_j \sum_{t=1}^n (1 - SVNNCDC_{jt}) \right)} \tag{16}$$

Step 4. Form the SVNNNPIVS (SVNN positive ideal value solution) and SVNNNNIVS (SVNN negative ideal value solution):

$$SVNNPIVS = (SVNNPIVS_1, SVNNPivs_2, \dots, SVNNPivs_n) \tag{17}$$

$$SVNNNIVS = (SVNNNIVS_1, SVNNNIVS_2, \dots, SVNNNIVS_n) \tag{18}$$

$$SVNNPIVS_j = (DT_j^{N+}, DI_j^{N+}, DF_j^{N+}) \tag{19}$$

$$SVNNNIVS_j = (DT_j^{N-}, DI_j^{N-}, DF_j^{N-}) \tag{20}$$

$$SVI(SVNNPIVS_j) = \max_i SVI(DR_{ij}^N) = \max_i SVI(DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N) \tag{21}$$

$$SVI(SVNNNIVS_j) = \min_i SVI(DR_{ij}^N) = \min_i SVI(DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N) \tag{22}$$

Step 5. Construct the SVNN combined distance measure (SVNNCDM) between

$DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNPIVS_j = (DT_j^{N+}, DI_j^{N+}, DF_j^{N+})$ in line with

SVNNHD and SVNNED.

$$SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNPivs_j) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|^2)} \right) \tag{23}$$

Step 6. Construct the SVNN combined distance measure (SVNNCDM) between

$DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNNIVS_j = (DT_j^{N-}, DI_j^{N-}, DF_j^{N-})$ in line with

SVNNHD and SVNNED.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &SVNNCDM \left(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}| \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2 \right)} \right) \quad (24)
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 7. Construct the SVNN weighted combined distance measure (SVNNWCDM) between $DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNPIVS_j = (DT_j^{N+}, DI_j^{N+}, DF_j^{N+})$ in line with SVNNHD and SVNNED and SVNN weighted combined distance measure (SVNNWCDM) between $DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNNIVS_j = (DT_j^{N-}, DI_j^{N-}, DF_j^{N-})$ in line with SVNNHD and SVNNED.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &SVNNWCDM \left(DR_i^N, SVNNPIVS \right) \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j SVNNCDM \left(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNPIVS_j \right) \right) \quad (25) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}| \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|^2 \right)} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &SVNNWCDM \left(DR_i^N, SVNNNIVS \right) \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j SVNNCDM \left(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j \right) \right) \quad (26) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}| \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left(|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2 \right)} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 8. Form the SVNN combined closeness coefficient (SVNNCCC):

$$\begin{aligned}
 SVNNCCC_i &= \frac{SVNNWCDM(DR_i^N, SVNNNIVS)}{\left(SVNNWCDM(DR_i^N, SVNNNIVS) + SVNNWCDM(DR_i^N, SVNNPIVS) \right)} \\
 &= \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (dw_j SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j))}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^n (dw_j SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j)) + \sum_{j=1}^n (dw_j SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNPIVS_j)) \right)} \\
 &= \frac{\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2)} \right) \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2)} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|^2)} \right) \right) \right)} \\
 &= \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2)} \right) \right)}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N-}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N-}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N-}|^2)} \right) \right) + \sum_{j=1}^n \left(dw_j \left(\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}| + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}| + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} (|DT_{ij}^N - DT_j^{N+}|^2 + |DI_{ij}^N - DI_j^{N+}|^2 + |DF_{ij}^N - DF_j^{N+}|^2)} \right) \right) \right)}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{27}$$

Step 9. Form the optimal choice in line with the largest SVNNCCC.

4. Illustrative example and comparative analysis

4.1 Illustrative example

Considering that the promotion time of the whole process consulting service model in the consulting service industry in China is relatively short, some consulting service units have insufficient understanding of this work model. In actual work, the whole process consulting service model cannot achieve satisfactory work results for owners. In order to improve the application effect of the whole Process engineering consulting service model, in the current development process of the consulting service industry, consulting service units can improve their own working ability by optimizing their own ideas, implementing corresponding rules and policies, building talent teams, carrying out resource integration work, etc., and provide impetus for the implementation of the whole process consulting service projects. Although the National Development and Reform Commission and the Ministry of Housing and Urban Rural Development jointly issued the Guiding Opinions on Promoting the Development of Process engineering consulting Services, the housing construction management departments in most regions have insufficient awareness of the policies and the degree of implementation is not deep enough, so that some government public resource service platforms have not opened businesses related to bidding transactions, In the process of engineering project promotion, only the segmented engineering consulting service transaction module has been established, which has hindered the development of the whole process engineering consulting service. At this stage, in order to effectively solve the above problems and achieve the smooth implementation of relevant policies, the competent construction departments, construction owners and consulting service enterprises in various regions need to fully recognize the advantages of the whole Process engineering consulting service model in the application process for engineering project survey, design, supervision, management and cost services, and the way to open the whole Process engineering consulting service module by the local government's public resource service platform, Ensure the smooth implementation of the whole process engineering consulting project. Then, in the process of carrying out subsequent consulting services, the coherence of engineering consulting services is improved by constructing the entire industry chain, providing support for the improvement of the quality of subsequent engineering construction activities. Although the consulting service enterprises, owners and regulators can carry out their work based on the Guiding Opinions on Promoting the Development of process engineering consulting Services in the actual work process, due to the relatively short application time of the whole process engineering consulting service model in China, each entity may lack a mature contract model in the process of carrying out the whole process engineering consulting services, and disputes arise. In order to effectively solve the above problems, in the current process of engineering consulting services, consulting service units can strengthen communication and negotiation between various entities based on the actual needs of the engineering project and traditional engineering consulting contracts, and clarify the rights and responsibilities of different participating units. Specifically, in order to minimize the probability of conflicts and disputes,

during the contract signing process, each participating entity needs to refine the issues of defining the rights and responsibilities of each entity, the requirements for clause performance, and dispute resolution clauses, in order to achieve effective division of the rights and responsibilities of each participating entity. At the same time, when negotiating related business, consulting service units can, on the basis of clarifying relevant systems and policies, complete consulting fee negotiation activities that can meet the requirements of the owner based on factors such as the scale and complexity of the project and the scope of the engineering consultation. Then, by recording the negotiation results in the contract, economic disputes can be avoided. The quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is MAGDM. In this work, the quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is formed through SVNN-CTOPSIS technique. There are five whole process engineering consulting service modes $DY_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)$ which are evaluated through three experts $DX = \{DX_1, DX_2, DX_3\}$ with equal weight values in light with four attributes: ① DZ_1 is the resource integration for whole process engineering consulting service; ② DZ_2 is the talent team construction for whole process engineering consulting service; ③ DZ_3 is the work ability for whole process engineering consulting service; ④ DZ_4 is the management cost for whole process engineering consulting service. The DZ_4 is cost type. Then, the SVNN-CTOPSIS model is formed to achieve the optimal whole process engineering consulting service mode.

Step 1. Form group SVNN-matrix $DR^{(k)} = (DR_{ij}^{(k)})_{5 \times 4} (k = 1, 2, 3)$ in light with linguistic scales (See Table 1) as in Table 2-4. The single SVNN-matrix is achieved in Table 5.

Table 1. Linguistic scale and SVNNs

Linguistic scales	SVNNs
Exceedingly Terrible-DET	(0.0000, 1.0000, 1.0000)
Very Terrible-DVT	(0.1000, 0.9000, 0.9000)
Terrible-DT	(0.3000, 0.7000, 0.7000)
Medium-DM	(0.5000, 0.5000, 0.5000)
Well-DW	(0.7000, 0.3000, 0.3000)
Very Well-DVW	(0.9000, 0.1000, 0.1000)
Exceedingly Well-DEW	(1.0000, 0.0000, 0.0000)

Table 2. SVNN-matrix from DX_1

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	DT	DVW	DVT	DM
DY ₂	DVW	DW	DM	DVT
DY ₃	DW	DM	DT	DVW
DY ₄	DM	DW	DVW	DVT
DY ₅	DVT	DVT	DVW	DM

Table 3. SVNN-matrix from DX_2

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	DVW	DW	DVT	DM
DY ₂	DM	DW	DVT	DVW
DY ₃	DM	DT	DVW	DW
DY ₄	DVT	DM	DVW	DT
DY ₅	DT	DW	DM	DVW

Table 4. SVNN-matrix from DX_3

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	DVW	DVT	DT	DW
DY ₂	DW	DT	DM	DM
DY ₃	DVW	DT	DM	DW
DY ₄	DVT	DM	DW	DVT
DY ₅	DT	DVW	DW	DM

Table 5. $DR = [DR_{ij}]_{5 \times 4}$

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	(0.45, 0.49, 0.41)	(0.47, 0.36, 0.48)	(0.43, 0.28, 0.32)	(0.48, 0.36, 0.39)
DY ₂	(0.40, 0.28, 0.34)	(0.69, 0.31, 0.38)	(0.39, 0.34, 0.46)	(0.56, 0.48, 0.45)
DY ₃	(0.58, 0.46, 0.37)	(0.56, 0.39, 0.46)	(0.48, 0.35, 0.39)	(0.25, 0.34, 0.43)

DY ₄	(0.43, 0.19, 0.31)	(0.49, 0.43, 0.52)	(0.56, 0.49, 0.47)	(0.53, 0.37, 0.49)
DY ₅	(0.51, 0.28, 0.16)	(0.54, 0.29, 0.34)	(0.63, 0.26, 0.35)	(0.67, 0.43, 0.36)

Step 2. Form the $DR = [DR_{ij}]_{5 \times 4}$ into standardized $DR^N = [DR_{ij}^N]_{5 \times 4}$ (See Table 6).

Table 6. The $DR^N = [DR_{ij}^N]_{5 \times 4}$

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	(0.45, 0.49, 0.41)	(0.47, 0.36, 0.48)	(0.43, 0.28, 0.32)	(0.39, 0.36, 0.48)
DY ₂	(0.40, 0.28, 0.34)	(0.69, 0.31, 0.38)	(0.39, 0.34, 0.46)	(0.45, 0.48, 0.56)
DY ₃	(0.58, 0.46, 0.37)	(0.56, 0.39, 0.46)	(0.48, 0.35, 0.39)	(0.43, 0.34, 0.25)
DY ₄	(0.43, 0.19, 0.31)	(0.49, 0.43, 0.52)	(0.56, 0.49, 0.47)	(0.49, 0.37, 0.53)
DY ₅	(0.51, 0.28, 0.16)	(0.54, 0.29, 0.34)	(0.63, 0.26, 0.35)	(0.36, 0.43, 0.67)

Step 3. Form the weight numbers in light with CRITIC (Table 7).

Table 7. The achieved weight

Attributes	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
weight numbers	0.2803	0.3002	0.2573	0.1622

Step 4. Form the SVN NNPIVS and SVN NNNI VS (Table 8):

Table 8. The SVN NNPIVS and SVN NNNI VS

	DZ ₁	DZ ₂
SVN NNPIVS	(0.58, 0.46, 0.37)	(0.69, 0.31, 0.38)
SVN NNNI VS	(0.40, 0.28, 0.34)	(0.47, 0.36, 0.48)
	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
SVN NNPIVS	(0.63, 0.26, 0.35)	(0.49, 0.37, 0.53)
SVN NNNI VS	(0.39, 0.34, 0.46)	(0.36, 0.43, 0.67)

Step 5. Calculate the $SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNPIVS_j)$ between $DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNPIVS_j = (DT_j^{N+}, DI_j^{N+}, DF_j^{N+})$ in line with SVNNHD and SVNNED (Table 9).

Table 9. $SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNPIVS_j)$.

Alternatives	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	0.4601	0.2837	0.3718	0.5046
DY ₂	0.5183	0.0000	0.4138	0.3371
DY ₃	0.0000	0.3168	0.4446	0.3653
DY ₄	0.4857	0.3760	0.6098	0.0000
DY ₅	0.4208	0.4284	0.0000	0.4551

Step 6. Calculate the $SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j)$ between $DR_{ij}^N = (DT_{ij}^N, DI_{ij}^N, DF_{ij}^N)$ and $SVNNNIVS_j = (DT_j^{N-}, DI_j^{N-}, DF_j^{N-})$ in line with SVNNHD and SVNNED (Table 10).

Table 10. $SVNNCDM(DR_{ij}^N, SVNNNIVS_j)$.

Alternatives	DZ ₁	DZ ₂	DZ ₃	DZ ₄
DY ₁	0.4514	0.0000	0.3647	0.4950
DY ₂	0.0000	0.3689	0.0000	0.3307
DY ₃	0.4128	0.3108	0.4059	0.4465
DY ₄	0.4765	0.2783	0.5982	0.3583
DY ₅	0.5085	0.4202	0.4361	0.0000

Step 7. Construct the SVNNWCDM from the SVNNPIVS and SVNNNIVS (Table 11).

Table 11. The SVNNWCDM from the SVNNPIVS and SVNNNIVS

$SVNNWCDM(DR_i^N, SVNNPIVS)$	$SVNNWCDM(DR_i^N, SVNNNIVS)$

DY ₁	0.3916	0.3006
DY ₂	0.3064	0.1644
DY ₃	0.2687	0.3858
DY ₄	0.4059	0.4291
DY ₅	0.3204	0.3809

Step 8. Form the SVNNCCC (Table 12).

Table 12. The SVNNCCC

	SVNNCCC	Order
DY ₁	0.4343	4
DY ₂	0.3491	5
DY ₃	0.5895	1
DY ₄	0.5139	3
DY ₅	0.5432	2

Step 9. In light with SVNNCCC, the obtained order is: $DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$ and DY_3 is the optimal whole process engineering consulting service mode.

4.2. Comparative analysis

The formed SVNN-CTOPSIS model is compared with SVNNWA model [55], SVNNWG model [55], SVNWBPM operator [58], SVNWGBPM operator[58], SVNN-WASPAS technique [59] and SVNN-TODIM technique [60], SVNN-GRA method[61], SVNN-VIKOR technique[62] and SVNN-CODAS technique [63]. The sufficient comparative results are verified in Table 17 and Figure 2.

Table 17. Order for different models

	Order
SVNNWA model [55]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$
SVNNWG model [55]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_1 > DY_4 > DY_2$
SVNWBPM operator [58]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$
SVNWGBPM operator[58]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_1 > DY_4 > DY_2$
SVNN-WASPAS technique [59]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$
SVNN-TODIM technique [60]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_1 > DY_4 > DY_2$
SVNN-GRA method [61]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$

SVNN-VIKOR technique [62]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$
SVNN-CODAS technique [63]	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$
SVNN-CTOPSIS model	$DY_3 > DY_5 > DY_4 > DY_1 > DY_2$

Figure 2. Order for different models

Through the above analysis, it could be seen that the order of these models is slightly different, however, these models have the same optimal whole process engineering consulting service mode and worst whole process engineering consulting service mode. This verifies the SVNN-CTOPSIS model is effective. Thus, the main advantages of the conducted SVNN-CTOPSIS model are formed: (1) the formed SVNN-CTOPSIS not only formed the uncertainty in MAGDM, but also portrays the combined distance measures from the SVNNNPIVS and SVNNNNIVS during the quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes. (2) the formed SVNN-CTOPSIS conducted the different behavior of the SVNNHD and SVNNED model as MAGDM techniques when they are combined.

5. Conclusion

The whole Process engineering consulting is a mode of providing all-round and full life cycle engineering consulting services for engineering construction projects from the perspective of the overall value appreciation of the project in order to effectively achieve the value objectives of engineering construction projects, which is also an international practice. With the rapid development of China's engineering construction industry, the scale of engineering projects continues to expand, and the complexity of engineering continues to increase. This poses serious challenges to China's engineering consulting industry. The previous fragmented engineering consulting model is no longer suitable for the new national conditions, nor can it cope with the international development of China's engineering

consulting industry both domestically and internationally. Seamless integration with the international engineering consulting industry, large-scale implementation of the whole Process engineering consulting model is imperative. The quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is MAGDM. In this paper, the SVNN-CTOPSIS model based on SVNNHD and SVNNED is formed to cope with the MAGDM. The CRITIC model is utilized to obtain the weight numbers in light with the SVNNHD and SVNNED under SVNSs. Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is employed to verify SVNN-CTOPSIS model. The main contributions of this study are formed: (1) the CRITIC model is formed to obtain the weight numbers in light with SVNNHD and SVNNED; (2) the SVNN-CTOPSIS model is formed in light with SVNNHD and SVNNED under SVNSs; (3) Finally, numerical example and comparative analysis for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes is utilized to verify SVNN-CTOPSIS model.

There may be some possible research limitations for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes, which could be further conducted in our future research contents: (1) It is a worthwhile research contents to conduct prospect theory[64-70] for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes under SVNSs; (2) It is also worthwhile research contents to conduct regret theory[71-77] for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes under SVNSs environment; (3) In subsequent research contents, the application of SVNSs needs to be formed with consensus issues [78-83] for quality evaluation of whole process engineering consulting service modes.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Science and Technology Research Program of Chongqing Municipal Education Commission under grant No. KJQN202204304, KJQN202303901, KJQN202303906) and the Education Science Planning Project of Chongqing, China under grant No. K23ZG3230200).

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Received: Mar 1, 2024. Accepted: May 29, 2024